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ETHICAL DECISIONS AND EMPLOYEES' EFFICIENCY OF HOTELS IN LAGOS STATE

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ABSTRACT:

The relevance of the hotel industry as an instrument for economic generation in countries cannot be over-emphasized. Despite its importance, hotel industry in Lagos State is facing a variety of challenges that are ethically based. Managers of the hotel industry in Lagos are seen to embrace unethical communication, not keeping to employees' right, practicing organisational injustices, embracing unethical leadership, and training among others. These unethical practices have undermining effects on employees' efficiency. Studies that examine the link between dimensions of ethical decisions on employees' efficiency in the hotel industry in Nigeria, particularly in Lagos State, have not been reported. The above mentioned practical and theoretical gaps are the justification for this study. The research population comprised the 792 registered hotels in Lagos State out of which 63 of the hotels selected through systematic random sampling. Taro Yamane formula was used to determine the sample size of 330 staffs out of 1,624 staffs in selected hotels in Lagos State. Structured questionnaires were used to collect the data, and analysed using Multiple Regression. The tested hypothetical relationship between dimensions of ethical decision on employees' efficiency shows that all the four dimensions of ethical decisions has positive and significant relationship with employees' efficiency. It is concluded that the practices of ethical communication; organisational justice; ethical leadership; and ethical training are therapies for employee efficiency in the hotel industry.

KEYWORDS:

Ethical Decision, Employees' Efficiency, Hotel industry, Lagos State.

Introduction

The hotel industry is the last hope of every traveller visiting a place outside their original place of abode. Globally, hotel investment continues to increase steadily, totalling US\$ 66.8 billion in 2021 (Jones Lang LaSalle's (JLL), 2022). The industry globally is predicted to experience annual revenue growth of US\$ 645.44 billion in 2021 to US\$ 784.33 billion in 2022 (Report Linker, 2022). In the United States, the hotel industry contributed a total of US\$ 659 billion to the GDP and US\$186 billion in Federal, State, and Local taxes (Oxford Economics, 2019). In the United Kingdom, the worth of the hotel industry is put at £5.8 billion in 2021 (Oxford Economics for the British Hospitality Association, 2022). In the context of Nigeria, the hotel industry has attracted significant investment putting at over US\$3 billion in the past five years (PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2017). The projected increase in hotel rooms in Nigeria, according to PricewaterhouseCoopers (2019) sees overall hotel room revenue expand at a 22.6% compound annual rate of \$US1.1 billion in 2019 from \$448 million in 2014. The indices highlighted above show that the hotel industry is a mature industry with significant positive impacts on the service economics of countries globally, and Nigeria in particular. Considering trends of employees' efficiency in the hotel industry, employees' of hotel industries in the developed economies performed reasonably well. However, with respect to efficiency of the hotel employees in some African countries, recent reports shows that efficiency of hotel industry in some countries in Sub-Sahara Africa looks good and promising except for Nigeria (PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2016, 2018). In the last five years, the efficiency of hotel employees in Nigeria had consistently experienced a decline despite huge investment attracted to the industry.

Horner (2016) opines that organisations whose management stakeholders embraces the culture of ethical decisions tend to increase the efficiency of their employees. Previous studies had researched the link between the dimensions of ethical communication and employees' efficiency in respect of employees of tertiary educational institutions in Thailand (Pongton&Suntrayuth, 2019); Turkey (Gulnar, 2007), and Tennessee, United States (Sharma, Lampley, and Good, 2015). Studies had also examined the correlation between ethical decisions and employees' efficiency among blue collar workers in the textile, plastics, and automotive industries in Asia (Bulutlar&Kamasak, 2008). Asides, the relationship between ethical decisions and employees' efficiency in respect of workers of government agencies in the Northern State of Malaysia was also reported (Desa&Asaari, 2019). The gap essentially is that, limited study in this domain have been reported in respect of the hotel industry in Lagos state. In view of unethical decisions culture among the various levels of the hotel employees' in Nigeria and more so in Lagos State necessitate this study.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

The Meaning of Ethical Decisions

Watts, Medeiros, McIntosh, and Mulhearn(2021) opined that ethical decisions involves adherence to accepted moral standards. It explains a process that seeks to maximize utility and minimize bias. Elm and Radin (2011); and Selart and Johansen (2011) defined ethical decisions as behavioral practices that is both legal and morally acceptable to the larger society. It is pertinent to state that the need to influence responsible behavioris becoming increasingly critical to deal with 'knotty ethical challenges" (Hartman&DesJardins, 2011). Ferrell, Fraedrich and Ferrell (2011) posits that ethical decisions involve value judgments and collective agreement about acceptable patterns of behavior in a workplace. This is in line with Kohlberg's model that suggested that individual's progress through certain stages of moral development regarding how they reason through moral problems using a cognitive framework that develops as the individual matures. Bon, Volkema and Ferreira da Silva

(2017) defined unethical decisions as the expression of one's willingness or commitment to engage in a behaviour adjudged not to violate generally-accepted societal moral norms. Thomson, Adams and Sartori (2005) defined ethical decision as recognizing a moral issue, moral judgment, moral intent and moral behaviour.

The Concept of Employees' Efficiency

Employees' efficiency is defined by Sabir, Iqbal, Rehman, Shah, and Yameen (2012) as the achievement of specified tasks against predetermined or identified standards of accuracy, completeness, cost and speed. Efficiency refers to the employees' output rate and is the ability to accomplish tasks before deadline (Afshan, Sobia, Kamran & Nasir, 2012). Karakas (2010) stated that efficiency explains the rate at which job is being achieved in terms of accuracy, and completeness over a specified period of time. Taormina and Gao (2009) indicated that efficiency refers to obtaining the most output from the least amount of input. Tsai, et al. (2010) argued that efficiency refers to the employees' speed in customer service. According to the authors, employees' speed can translate to output rate. Output rate in this context implies the quality or quantity of job, job design and others (Kikoito, 2014). The index in these information shows that hotel efficiency is an important concept in human resource management for measuring overall hotel employee performance.

Theoretical Framework

Deontology Theory: The theory of Deontological capital was proposed in the early 1960s by a German philosopher, Immanuel Kant (Bauer & Zimmermann 1999). The theory was originally used in the field of organisational behaviour to explain human factors that determines satisfaction and by extension performance in a workplace (Bauer & Zimmermann 1999). The deontological capital theory holds that, rather than the ends justifying the means, "other features besides those of goodness determine the justness of the actions (Becker, 1994). Deontologists are also known as Universalists, because a decision will not change based on the number of people positively or negatively affected by the outcome, but will remain constant based on the rightness of the action. In this system, there are things which are intrinsically good or bad, though what these good and bad may vary based on indifferent beliefs. Deontologists also argue that there are relationship ties "that intrinsically enrich moral life" and impose certain responsibilities on those within the relationship. This is the logic which argues that employers bear a responsibility to care for their employees and customers, specifically, rather than looking, as a utilitarian would, for what would benefit the whole of society. Lately, the Deontologists theory has gained more prominence in the workplace environment and increased productivity. The theory argued that human capital is treated with sense of justice, training, and managed by selfless leaders, could enhance workers efficiency.

As it applies to the current study, the theory argued that hotel organisations whose managers and owners practices ethical principles (i.e. ethical communication, ethical organisational justice, ethical leadership, and ethical training) tend to increase worker's efficiency. Given the applicability of this theory to this study, the theory stands to be adopted for the study.

Empirical Review and Hypotheses Development

Ethical Communication and Employees' Efficiency

Previous studies had examined the link between ethical communication and employees' efficiency among employees of tertiary educational institutions in Thailand (Pongton & Suntrayuth, 2019); Turkey (Gulnar, 2007), and Tennessee, United States (Sharma et al., 2015). Studies were also conducted to examine the correlation between ethical communication and employees' efficiency among blue collar workers in the textile, plastics, automotive, and food and beverage industries in

Asia (Bulutlar&Kamasak, 2008). Besides, the relationship between ethical communication and employees' efficiency in respect of workers of government agencies in the Northern State of Malaysia was also reported (Desa&Asaari, 2019). However, limited study in this domain have been reported in respect of the hotel industry and more so in emerging economy like Nigeria. In view, ineffective communication occasioned by poor adoption of ethical communication culture among the various levels of the hotel employees' in Nigeria and more so in Lagos state necessitated this study. Therefore, this study assumes the following hypothesis:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between ethical communication and employees' efficiency of hotel workers in Lagos state.

Ethical Organisational Justice and Employees' Efficiency

Research had shown that much study on the link between ethical organisational justice and employees' efficiency among public service employees in Indonesia (Juarsah, et al., 2019); Košice, Slovak republic (2018), and Vietnam (Ha Tran, 2020). Studies was also conducted to examine the correlation between ethical organisational justice and employees' efficiency among secondary school teachers in Iraq (Ghran, et al., 2019); faculty of education university of Negeri Surabaya (Lestari, 2017), and Tehran Payame Noor University (Lotfi& Pour, 2013). Besides, the relationship between ethical organisational justice and employees' efficiency in respect of workers of banking industry in Port Harcourt Nigeria was also reported (Okocha & Anyanwu, 2016). This implies that, limited study in this domain have been reported in respect of the hotel industry and more so in emerging economy like Nigeria. In view of promotion, reward, and career development injustices that characterized the hotel industries in Nigeria and more so in Lagos state necessitated this study. Therefore, this study assumes the following hypothesis:

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between ethical organisational justice and employees' efficiency of hotel workers in Lagos state.

Ethical Leadership and Employees' Efficiency

Previous studies had shown that much study on the link between ethical leadership and employees' efficiency among employees of micro and medium enterprises in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria (Bello, et al., 2018); industry and trade organization in Fars Province (Pournofrad&Mohammadian, 2018); Malaysia (Panigrahi and Al-Nashash, 2019). Studies was also conducted to examine the correlation between ethical leadership and employees' efficiency in the Ghana education service (Salifu, et al., 2022); universities in Pakistan (Shehzad, et al., 2022). This shows that, limited study in this domain have been reported in respect of the hotel industry and more so in emerging economy like Nigeria. In view of unethical leadership practices such as sexual harassment of female employees, fraud, and discrimination in staff reward system among others that characterized the hotel industries in Nigeria and more so in Lagos state necessitated this study. Therefore, this study assumes the following hypothesis:

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between ethical leadership and employees' efficiency in the hotel industry in Lagos state.

Ethical Training and Employees' Efficiency

Previous research had reported the link between ethical training and employees' efficiency among oil company employees in Iran (Karimi & Nejad, 2018); Ethiopian management institute (Lemma and Mekonnen, 2018); employees in private and public sectors in Malaysia (Vasudevan, 2014). Studies was also conducted to examine the correlation between ethical training and employees' efficiency

among academic staff of Bayero University, Kano Nigeria (Nuhu, et al., 2018); Uganda management institute (Picho, 2014). This shows that, limited study in this domain have been reported in respect of the hotel industry and more so in emerging economy like Nigeria. In view of the fact that hotel owners in Lagos state pay little or no attention to staff training needs necessitated this study. Therefore, this study assumes the following hypothesis:

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between ethical training and employees' efficiency in the hotel industry in Lagos state.

Methodology

Research Design: Quantitative research design is a survey technique used to measure specific characteristics through structured questionnaire from a representative sample, so that the result can be generalised for the entire population (Davis, 2000; Salih et al., 2010). As it applies to this study, the researcher used structured questionnaire to determine the correlation between dimensions of ethical decisions, and employees' efficiency in respect of hotels in Lagos State.

Population and Sample Unit: A target population in research is the population that the researcher would ideally like to generalise the findings of the study (Gay & Airasian, 2000). It includes the larger group to which researcher hope to apply the result of a study from a smaller group. As it relates to the present study, the research population of this study comprise of employees of the 792 registered hotels in the 20 LGAs in Lagos State. The sampling units that was used in this research work include employees of 63 registered hotels in the 20 LGAs in Lagos State. The sampled hotels were selected through a systematic random sampling technique. The researcher serially number all the 792 registered hotels in each of the 20 LGAs in Lagos State, and automatically picked the first hotel on the list in each of the LGAs while others were picked at an interval of 15 thus, 63 hotels were selected and used for the current study.

Sample Size : In this study, it is practically impossible for the researcher to sample the whole employees in each of the 63 selected hotels in the 20 LGAs in Lagos State hence, the researcher determined the proportion of the sample unit that constitutes the sample (i.e., the number of respondents which questionnaires will be administered to). Taro Yamane formula which is given as follows was adopted:

$$n = \frac{X}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n= sample size.

X= Observation Unit.

N= Population Size.

e= Sample Error or level of significance.

Therefore, to determine the sample size of the employees of the 63 selected hotels vis-à-vis the population of the staff, the present study conceded to the method of proportional allocation suggested in Kothari (1990). The concept of propositional allocation suggested that the size of samples from different strata are kept propositional to the sizes of the strata. Before applying the Taro Yamane formula as suggested in Sekaran (2003), the researcher contacted the management of the 63 selected hotels to

obtain the total number of employees on their payroll thus; the populations (N) size of 1, 624 were obtained. The sample size (n) of staff per each of the 63 selected hotels (i.e., $n_1, \dots, n_{63}$) to be drawn from the population (N) of 1,624 were determined per each of the hotels. The results show that the sample size of the hotel employees that participated in the filling of the questionnaire is 330 staff. In view of this, the researcher visited each of the 63 targeted hotels in the 20 LGAs in Lagos state with the aid of research assistance and thus, administered the structured questionnaires to the respondents until the sample size for each of the hotel is met.

Research Instrument: Part 1 of the questionnaire show the personal information of the respondents. The items to be used to characterise the respondents are: gender, marital status, religion, educational qualification, and work experience. Part 2 of the questionnaire comprises of four dimensions of ethical decisions: Ethical communication scale used in this study was adapted from 9 items standardized communication audits in Downs and Adrian (1997). **Ethical Organisational Justice:** The 13 items questionnaire of organizational justice developed in Colquitt et al. (2001) was adopted, and modified into 7 items to be used in this study to measure ethical organisational justice in this study. **Ethical Leadership:** The Tourism and Hospitality Organizational Climate Scale revised by Manning, Davidson and Manning (2004) and used to measure the leadership climate within the fast food restaurant setting was adopted in this study. This scale comprised of 5 items question thus reworded and used for the purpose of this study. **Ethical Training:** The instrument of ethical training used in this study was adapted from the ethical training and job satisfaction survey technical manual of the East Carolina University. The instrument which consists of 46 items was developed by Steven (2004). For the current study, 6 items of ethical training were modified and used. All the items were measured on a 4-point Likert scale of 1 representing strongly disagree to 4 representing strongly agreed with respect to hotels in Lagos State.

Part 3 of the questionnaire is the measurement of employees' efficiency as of the following.

Employees' Efficiency: A eight items instrument developed by Gao and Taormina's (2002) will be adapted based on work efficiency literature in China. The adapted instrument consists of 5 items were measured on a 4-point Likert scale. Each item will be rated by the respondents from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agreed). The instrument was used to measure employees' efficiency as it applies to hotels in Lagos State.

Results and Findings

Respondents' demographic profile

A general profile of respondents' demographic statistics was analysed in this section. Table 1 shows the summary of the demographic features of the respondents used in this study.

Table 1: The Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Profile	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Marital Status		
1. Single	219	66.4
2. Married	108	32.7
3. Divorce	3	0.3

Religion		
1. Islam		
2. Christianity	237	71.8
3. Others	46	13.9
	47	14.2
Educational Qualification		
1. ND	117	35.5
2. HND / B.SC	103	31.2
3. PGD/M.Sc.	110	33.3
Gender		
1. Male		
2. Female	210	63.6
	120	36.4

Source: Researcher's Computation (2024).

In terms of marital status, Table 1 shows that 219 of the respondents are single (66.4%) while 108 are married (32.7%). The frequency of divorced participants is 3 representing .3%. This implies that the majority of the participants in this study are singles. Table 1 further shows that the religion distribution of respondents used in this study is: Islam, 237 respondents (71.8%), Others, 47 respondents (14.2%), and Christianity, 46 respondents (13.9%). This shows that the majority of participants in this study are Muslims while Christians and Others are very few. The age distribution of respondents reveals that the participants between the ages of 17-26 are the largest group, comprising 72 participants (44.7%). The analysis further shows that about 55 respondents (34.2%) are between the age of 27- 35, while those ages 36-44 are 32 (19.9%) while 46-above years of age are 2 (1.2%). This shows that the majority of the participants used for this study have their age range within 17-26 years, followed by those with age bracket 27-35. The analysis of participant's distribution by education qualification shows that about 117 of the respondents have National Diploma (ND) put at 35.5%. About 103 of the respondents have HND/B.Sc degree put at 31.2% while 110 of the respondents have a Post Graduate Diploma/Master of Science (33.3%). This implies that majority of the participants used in this study are holders of Higher National Diploma (HND) / B.Sc, followed by those with MBA/ Master's Degrees. The implication of this is that employees of Hotel industry are persons of high education attainment contrary to general assumption that hotel workers are people of low academic qualification achievers. The analysis as shown in Table 4.1 revealed that 210 of the respondents (63.6%) are male while 120 of the respondents (36.4%) are female. This implies that the majority of the respondents used in this study are male. The implication of this is that Hotels industry in Lagos State are male dominated.

Bivariate analysis

This is to determine the relationship between each of the four dimensions of ethical decision and employees' efficiency in the hotel industry in Lagos state, hence objectives of this study. Four hypotheses (H_{01} - H_{04}) were tested and the results of the analysis are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Correlations of Ethical Communication, Organisational Justice, Leadership and Training and Employees' Efficiency

Variables	R	P	Level	Hypothesis
Employees' Efficiency (EYE)	-	-	-	-
Ethical communication (ETC)	0.373	0.000	Low	H _A = Accepted
Ethical Org. Justice (ETJ)	0.472	0.000	Low	H _A = Accepted
Ethical Leadership (ETL)	0.330	0.000	Low	H _A = Accepted
Ethical Training (ETT)	0.605	0.000	High	H _A = Accepted

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher's Computation (2024).

The results as shown in Table 2 depicted that the four measures of Ethical Decision have a positive and significant relationship with Employees' Efficiency in respect to hotels in Lagos State. Thus, Ethical communication (ETC) ($r = 0.373$; $p = 0.000$); Ethical Org. Justice (ETJ) ($r = 0.472$; $p = 0.000$); Ethical Leadership (ETL) ($r = 0.330$; $p = 0.000$); and Ethical Training (ETT) ($r = 0.605$; $p = 0.000$). In terms of the strength of the relationship, the results show that all the four dimensions of ethical decisions have a low correlation with employees' efficiency except ethical training that has high correlation in respect of hotels in Lagos State.

Table 3: Model Summary of Ethical Communication, Organisational Justice, Leadership and Training and Employees' Efficiency^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.684 ^a	.241	.524	2.560	.341	22.143	4	325	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), ETT, ETC, ETJ, ETL

b. Dependent Variable: EYE.

Source: Researcher's Computation (2024).

From Table 3, it was described that the R-square for the model is .241 which implies that the four dimensions of ethical decision explained 20.1% of the variance in employees' job efficiency in respect to hotels in Lagos State. Therefore, the remaining 79.9% is due to other factors and residuals. Also, the multiple R ($R = .684$) revealed a significant high relationship between independent variables (i.e. four dimensions ethical decision) and the dependent variable (employees' job efficiency).

Table 4: ANOVA^a Ethical Communication, Organisational Justice, Leadership and Training and Employees' Efficiency

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4462.897	4	1115.724	20.143	.000 ^b
	Residual	.1367.001	325	.8763		
	Total	4462.897	329			

a. Dependent Variable: EYE

b. Predictors: (Constant), ETT, ETC, ETJ, ETL

Source: Researcher's Computation (2024).

Table 4 indicates that the result of the analysis shows that F value is significant ($F= 20.143$, $p=.000$). This shows that the model is valid. Thus, based on the findings it can be concluded that there was a linear relationship between the four dimensions of ethical decision and employees' efficiency of hotels in Lagos.

Table 5: The coefficient contributions of Ethical Communication, Organisational Justice, Leadership and Training and Employees' Efficiency

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	6.580	2.112		3.115	.002	2.408	10.752					
	ETC	.032	.173	.029	.186	.853	-.309	.374	.373	.015	.000	.672	1.489
	ETJ	.090	.146	.098	.619	.537	-.198	.379	.472	.050	.000	.589	1.699
	ETL	.195	.072	.187	2.690	.008	.052	.338	.330	.211	.756	.571	1.751
	ETT	.381	.064	.435	5.981	.000	.255	.507	.605	.432	.000	.606	1.651

a. Dependent Variable: EYE

Source: Author Computation (2024).

In differentiating the contribution of each independent variable, Beta values are used. As illustrated in the standardized coefficient column in Table 5, Ethical Organisational Justice (ETJ) has the highest contributions put at (.098) to employees' efficiency, followed by Ethical Training (ETT) (.435).

Discussion of Findings

The first objective of the present study examined the relationship between ethical communication and employees' efficiency of hotels in Lagos. The results of this study revealed that a positive and significant relationship exists between ethical communication and employees' efficiency in respect of hotels in Lagos State. The outcome of this study conform to the previous as reported in Djordjevic, Milanovic and Stankovic (2021) that studied the influence of ethical communication on employees' efficiency of employees of Southeast of Serbia in the Republic of Serbia. The findings showed that there is positive correlation between ethical communication and employees' efficiency. Desa and Asaari (2019) studied the correlation between ethical communication, employees' efficiency, and job

satisfaction among workers in the department of trade union affairs in the Northern State of Malaysia. The study concludes that ethical communication has a positive and significant relationship with employees' efficiency and job satisfaction among workers in the study area. Bulutlar and Kamasak (2008) investigated the relationship between ethical communication and employees' efficiency of blue collar workers in manufacturing companies operating in textile, plastics, automotive, and food and beverage in Asia. The study revealed a clear positive and significant relationship between ethical communication and employees' efficiency.

The second objective of the present study examined the relationship between ethical organisational justice and employees' efficiency of hotels in Lagos. The results of this study revealed that a positive and significant relationship exists between ethical organisational justice and employees' efficiency in respect of hotels in Lagos State. The outcome of this study conform to the previous studies as reported in Juarsah, Masdupi and Syahrizal (2019) studied the effect of ethical organizational justice, trust in bosses and employees' efficiency at Persero in Indonesia. The result of the study showed that ethical organizational justice has a significant and positive effect on employees' efficiency. Galván-Vela, Ravina-Ripoll, Ahumada-Tello and Tobar-Pesantez (2022) studied the impact of dimensions of ethical organizational justice on employees' efficiency in emerging economy. The result found the four of the dimensions has positive and significant relationship with employees' efficiency. Ha Tran (2020) studied the relationship between organisational justice, employee satisfaction, and employee efficiency in respect of Vietnam. The result of the study show that organisational justice has a positive impact on employees' efficiency.

The third objective of the present study examined the relationship between ethical leadership and employees' efficiency of hotels in Lagos. The results of this study revealed that a positive and significant relationship exists between ethical leadership and employees' efficiency in respect of hotels in Lagos State. The outcome of this study conform to the previous studies as reported in Pourmofrad and Mohammadian (2017) that studied the effect of ethical leadership on the efficiency among employees of industry and trade organization of Fars province. The result of the study showed that there is a significant relationship between the dimension of ethical leadership and employees' efficiency. Panigrahi and Al-Nashash (2019) investigated quality leadership ethics and employees' efficiency in Malaysia. The result of the study showed that ethical leadership is one of the key attributes to increase employee's efficiency. Salifu¹, Zhu, and Rakib (2022) studied the relationship between ethical leadership style and employees' efficiency in the Ghana education service. Findings reveal that there is statistically significant positive relationship between ethical leadership style and job efficiency among employees at the Ghana education service.

The fourth objective of the present study examined the relationship between ethical training and employees' efficiency of hotels in Lagos. The results of this study revealed that a positive and significant relationship exists between ethical training and employees' efficiency in respect of hotels in Lagos State. The outcome of this study conform to the previous studies as reported in Karimi and Nejad (2018) that investigated the effect of organizational training on employees' efficiency of oil company employees in Iran. The findings showed that the quality of organizational training has a positive and significant effect on employees' efficiency. Lemma and Mekonnen (2018) examined effects of ethical training on employees' efficiency at Ethiopian management institute. The result showed that ethical training has positive and significant relationship with employees' efficiency. Vasudevan (2014) examined the relationship between training and efficiency of employees in private and public sectors in Malaysia. The result of the study showed that ethical training has positive and

significant influence on employee's efficiency. Nuhu, Salisu, Abubakar and Abdullahi (2018) investigated the correlation between ethical training and employees' efficiency among academic staff of Bayero University, Kano Nigeria. The findings of the study showed that ethical training affects employees' efficiency of the academic staff of Bayero University Kano, Nigeria.

Conclusions from the findings

Congruently, in accordance with the research objectives, and hypothesis predictions were developed in agreement with the previous literature that explored the contributions of various constructs towards explaining the relationship between the constructs in the context of hotels in Lagos. Fortunately, answers to these research objectives have been found; and all the proposed hypotheses investigated were found to be supported. It is therefore critical to state that the practices of ethical communication; organisational justice; ethical leadership; and ethical training in hotels in Lagos state will sustainably enhances employees' efficiency. It is concluded that managers of hotel establishment should put in place policy thrust that ensures ethical practices for enhance staff efficiency.

The researcher therefore recommends that future studies should replicate the outcome of the study in other States in Nigeria. One of the limitations of the current study is that only the staff of hotels in Lagos was focused, thus did not consider the perception of the impact of employees' performance from the customers' perspective. In view of this, the researcher recommended that future studies should increase the unit of analysis, and extend the study to other states of the federation for better and insightful information and results.

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